

ANALYSIS OF PRINCIPLES AND METHODS FOR ENHANCING THE RESISTANCE OF CONCRETE TO PHYSICAL AND/OR MECHANICAL IMPACT FOR THE POST-WAR RECONSTRUCTION OF AFFECTED CITIES OF UKRAINE

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Abstract: The principles and methods of improving the resistance of concrete to physical and/or mechanical impacts are highlighted in accordance with Principle 5 of Part 9 of EN 1504. The innovative technologies and tools described in EN 1504 are of practical importance for the reconstruction of damaged cities in Ukraine. An analysis was carried out of organizational and technological solutions for the repair of high-strength floors, based on existing scientific studies of modern European and American researchers, as well as specialized institutes and organizations.

Keywords: reconstruction of affected cities of Ukraine, repair of high-strength floors, concrete structures, improving concrete resistance.

The requirements faced by industrial and civil facilities in the post-war period create the need for the installation of strong, wear-resistant floors with improved flatness and crack resistance. Today, the issue of restoration, repair, and extension of the service life of high-strength concrete floors has become particularly relevant. As a result of the armed conflict in Ukraine, there is a tendency toward an increasing number of concrete floor structures being in unsatisfactory condition not only in older buildings but also in newly constructed facilities. An urgent issue is the implementation of European standards and their harmonization with national standards. Despite the measures adopted over the past year aimed at ensuring the reliability of buildings and structures in operation, many tasks to improve operational reliability remain unresolved, which undoubtedly confirms the relevance of the chosen topic.

The approach of Principle 5 of Part 9 of EN 1504 consists in increasing resistance to physical or mechanical impacts. According to EN 1504-9, this can be achieved by three methods, which are described below [6].

Method 5.1 involves coating the concrete surface to improve its physical resistance, for example, against abrasion or impact [10]. A schematic representation is shown in Figure 1. During surface preparation, concrete of insufficient quality must be replaced and cracks must be filled.

Figure 1 – Schematic representation of Method 5.1 before and after application [9]

To increase the physical resistance of the concrete surface, coatings with high strength and good adhesion to concrete are required, such as epoxy resins or similar polymers [1]. Mortars and concretes for improving physical resistance are classified under Method 5.3. Requirements for coatings for Method 5.1 are specified in EN 1504-2 [11]. These include abrasion resistance and impact strength for any intended use. Crack bridging is not usually prescribed, but in certain specific cases it may be required by the engineer. For physical and mechanical durability, small cracks passing from the concrete through the coating are often acceptable, provided the quality of the concrete is sufficiently high to prevent propagation along the crack boundary [2]. However, cracks often need to be sealed to prevent the ingress of harmful substances such as chlorides. In such cases, crack-bridging coating systems may provide a solution, but they must be more flexible, which reduces physical strength. Therefore, in situations where both physical resistance and crack protection are required, it is necessary to determine which of the eight methods of Principle 1 should additionally be applied [6]. With regard to durability, it should be taken into account that coatings subjected to abrasion or impact deteriorate over time depending on use. Therefore, regular inspections are recommended.

Method 5.2 is an alternative to coatings and uses impregnation to improve the physical resistance of the concrete surface [10]. A schematic representation of Method 5.2 is shown in Figure 2. During surface preparation, concrete of insufficient quality must be replaced and cracks must be filled [3]. The possibility of using the same material for impregnation, as well as for replacing damaged concrete and filling cracks, should be considered, as shown in Figure 2. As explained for Method 1.2, impregnation materials penetrate into the pores of the concrete and may form a thin film on the concrete surface. Special epoxy resins are usually used as impregnation materials [1]. Requirements for impregnation

products are specified in EN 1504-2. As with coatings, abrasion resistance and impact strength must be confirmed for this method [10]. Impregnations generally cannot bridge moving cracks [4]. If open cracks are not acceptable for other reasons, additional methods must be applied. The impregnation material hardens within the pores of the concrete and usually forms a thin hard film on the concrete surface. Therefore, it is generally sufficiently strong, depending on the conditions of use.

Figure 2 – Schematic representation of Method 5.2 before and after application [9]

Method 5.3 represents a third option to increase physical resistance — the addition of mortar or concrete to the concrete surface [10]. A schematic representation of Method 5.3 is shown in Figure 3. During surface preparation, concrete of insufficient quality must be replaced and cracks must be filled [3]. The tensile strength of the surface must be sufficient to achieve strong adhesion between the old concrete and the added layer of mortar or concrete. If the surface concrete is of very low quality, even the addition of an ordinary new concrete layer will increase physical resistance [5]. If high resistance to abrasion and impact is required, special mortars or concretes are available. Physical resistance can be increased by various measures, such as using low-porosity mixes, special hard aggregates, fibers, vacuum treatment, or combinations of these measures. Since this method was included in EN 1504-9 at a very late stage, mortars or concretes for Method 5.3 are not regulated in EN 1504-3 [7]. However, as already noted, many mortars and concretes with high resistance to abrasion and impact are available on the market [8]. To be able to select the appropriate product, the usage parameters must be specified in as much detail as possible. With regard to durability, again it should be taken into account that surfaces subjected to abrasion or impact deteriorate over time depending on usage. Therefore, regular inspections are recommended. To further increase physical resistance, impregnation in accordance with Method 5.2 may be applied over the added mortar or concrete.

Figure 3 – Schematic representation of Method 5.3 before and after application [9]

Thus, in designing repair works for high-strength floors in civil and industrial buildings, it is necessary to take into full account the inspection data on the technical condition of existing structures, to comply with technological requirements for the removal of defective and damaged areas, to ensure proper preparation for repair, and to use materials with equivalent properties. Only in this way can organizational and technological reliability of the parameters of the technological process and the optimal technical and economic performance be ensured in the reconstruction of damaged cities of Ukraine.

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